

Synthesis of 2-(2-Ethylamino-4-methylthiazol-5-yl)-benzimidazole

J. M. Singh and G. R. Chaudhry

Benzimidazole derivatives have been reported to possess trypanosomoidal¹ and spirocheticidal actions and are active against diseases caused by protozoa. Certain group, such as morpholinomethyl-, pyrrolidinomethyl-, when inserted in position 2 of benzimidazole, impart to them local anaesthetic property². Turk and Ueckert³ found 2-(thiazol-4-yl)-benzimidazole to be an effective anthelmintic agent for horses. Gupta and Singh⁴ prepared 2-(thiazol-2-yl)-benzimidazoles, but their biological activity was not reported. It was considered of interest to study the effect of introducing ethylamino and methyl groups in thiazole ring.

2-Amino-4-methyl-5-ethoxycarbonylthiazole⁵ was alkylated according to the method of Burmistrov and Krasovaskii⁶. The 2-ethylamino-4-methyl-5-ethoxycarbonylthiazole was condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine in presence of polyphosphoric acid.

2-Ethylamino-4-methyl-5-ethoxycarbonylthiazole.—Ethanol (1.5 ml) was added to 2-amino-4-methyl-5-ethoxycarbonylthiazole (1.9 g.) in 80% H₂SO₄ (30 ml). The mixture was heated on a water bath for 4 hr., poured on ice, and neutralised with alkali to furnish 2-ethylamino-4-methyl-5-ethoxycarbonylthiazole; yield 55%, m.p. 215°. (Found: N, 13.04; S, 14.92. C₉H₁₄O₂N₂S requires N, 13.08; S 14.95%),

2-(2-Ethylamino-4-methylthiazole-5-yl)-benzimidazole.—*o*-Phenylenediamine (1.1 g.) and the preceding thiazole (2.2 g.) were taken in polyphosphoric acid (30 ml), heated at 250° for 4 hr., poured on ice, and neutralised with NH₄OH. (conc.). The inorganic precipitate was removed. The filtrate on concentration provided a crude product. On crystallisation from ethanol and ethyl acetate 2-(2-ethylamino-4-methylthiazol-5-yl)-benzimidazole was obtained; m.p. 190°. (Found: N, 21.50; S 12.39. C₁₃H₁₄N₄S requires N, 21.70; S 12.40%).

1. Walter et al. (Winthrop Chemical Co.) U. S. P. 2242581/1941; *Chem. Abs.*, 1941, 35, 5648.
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5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2242
6. *Zhur. Obsh. Khim.*, 1964 34, 3022.